

Application of People Analytics for reducing human-related cyber risk in the context of Air Traffic Managers

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Abstract. The discipline of People Analytics (PA), which began as an innovative Human Resources (HR) methodology focused on managing workforce dynamics, has proven to be highly effective in optimising organisational processes and fostering employee skills development. Given the background of previous research findings in cybersecurity, this paper explores the potential of PA, in the context of Air Traffic Managers (ATM), to improve the efficiency of the training process in cybersecurity. The most problematic aspect of training in cybersecurity, but also from a general point of view, in big organisations is the optimisation of the Return on Training Investments (ROTI). This indicator, at a general level, involves three essential sources of costs: (i) class composition, (ii) long-term impact of training, and (iii) direct cybersecurity training costs. According to the Kirkpatrick/Phillips ROI model, element (i) is usually the prevalent training variable, and PA is more impactful here. The advantages of PA as an application of Learning Analytics (LA) are proven. We apply it as a method to increase the effectiveness of training as a cyber risk reduction method. By employing Machine Learning (ML) and data-driven strategies, PA can precisely identify the employee cluster most in need of training, ensuring that these interventions achieve maximum impact regarding cybersecurity improvements. The paper describes our solution's improvements over the classic training approach and its role and relationship in optimising class composition. Thanks to the EU-funded project SEC-AIRSPACE, this preliminary presentation reports unique design characteristics adopted by the authors for the ATM world.

Keywords: People Analytics, Air Traffic Managers, Cyber Risk, Training, Machine Learning.

1 Introduction.

1.1 Background.

The objective of the SEC-AIRSPACE project¹, financed by SESAR JU and the EU Commission, is to enable cyber-resilient Air Traffic Managers (ATMs), focusing on

¹ SESAR Joint Undertaking | SEC-AIRSPACE - Cyber Security Risk Assessment in virtualized AIRSPACE scenarios and stakeholders' awareness of building resilient ATM, <https://www.sesarju.eu/projects/sec-airspace>

reducing the risks of virtualisation and increasing data-sharing between all components of the ATM infrastructure and the relevant stakeholders. The digitalisation and modernisation of ATMs will bring many advantages to aviation, but these will come with challenges in managing cyber vulnerabilities. The project aims to introduce cyber security components into the state-of-the-art security risk assessment methodology (ies) currently used in ATMs. One of the key research areas the project investigates is People Analytics (PA) usage to increase cyber security awareness in ATM organisations. The project results will be validated and demonstrated through two real use cases involving relevant stakeholders. A preliminary presentation of the general project outcomes can be found in a recently published paper [1].

The term “People Analytics” does not refer to technology but to a novel, quantitative, evidence-based, and data-driven approach to managing the workforce [2]. From a cyber risk mitigation perspective, our PA-based solution is a component of the Training Process [1]. PA focuses on delivering classes optimised for cyber risk mitigation. Cyber risk is unevenly distributed among users in the workforce, with most risk events linked to a small group of users. The 2024 report "Exposing Human Risk" [3] supports this with statistics:

- Just 1% of users are behind 44% of all clicked phishing emails. 5% of users are responsible for 83.4% of all clicks.
- 1% of users are behind 92% of all malware events. 5% of users are responsible for all malware events. The remaining 95% had a clean record

We define the Training Process as a process aiming to enhance employee skills and knowledge, especially in cybersecurity. It involves identifying training needs through PA, developing targeted programs with the support of a Training Provider, and evaluating effectiveness.

A Training Provider delivers educational programs to improve participants' knowledge and skills. This role involves conducting training sessions (using a training paradigm in-person, online or recorded), managing classroom attendance, administering pre- and post-training evaluations, and creating practical scenarios utilising methods such as CSX for hands-on experience. The entire process is detailed in **Fig. 1**, outlining the roles of Human Resources (HR), CISO, training providers, CSX, and classes about a comprehensive risk reduction strategy.

The goal is to maximise Return on Training Investment (ROTI) by focusing on at-risk employees and aligning interventions with specific cyber risks. The process includes pre- and post-assessments of competencies, eventually using a Cyber Security Exercise (CSX) and monitoring course attendance. A CSX, a type of learn-by-doing, offers practical cybersecurity experience by simulating realistic cyber threats. Participants apply their skills in a controlled setting to improve problem-solving, decision-making, and understanding of cybersecurity concepts for real-world challenges [4] [5].

Fig. 1 represents a typical Training Process, and the role later played by the PA is performed by HR, who is eventually advised by the local CISO. However, HR operates at its best; its decisions are made by leveraging its knowledge and comprehension of the training process's risks, costs, and consequences. The creation of training classes

(i.e., the user segmentation) follows subjective or non-analytic criteria [6] [7]. A tool to support this HR decision process would be helpful.

While training services have been available on the market for several years, despite some debate over their effectiveness, there is a consensus that efficient training against cyber risk is achievable. Efficient training means an efficient Training Process.

From a general point of view, Training, Awareness, and Learning—three distinct methods for sharing knowledge—can effectively reduce risks associated with human behaviour. Training, awareness, and learning are ways to reduce risks from human behaviour. Current strategies often rely on traditional methods to handle cyber risks through established procedures, including but not limited to MITRE ATT&CK [8], ISO/IEC 27005 [9] and SecRAM [10].

Fig. 1. Schematic representation of the Training Process loop. The risk_j is a generic human-related risk, among those described by MITRE ATT&CK or SecRAM taxonomies.

1.2 Cybersecurity issues and human elements.

Cybersecurity issues related to the human element are wide-ranging and impact any action or error involving an organisation's cyber risk. This includes regular employees as well as the cybersecurity team. Wherever people are involved, such as in the IT or OT sphere, there is a potential cybersecurity problem [11]: the situation should be approached with careful attention to ethical principles, fostering trust between employers and employees, and adhering to labour regulations, in line with the European DOGANA² project's findings.

Organisations with complex structures, different roles, and heterogeneous technologies are generally more susceptible to social engineering attacks than others. ATMs are among them. Changing behaviours and habits through targeted and effective awareness programs can be challenging. It may take a significant amount of time, leading to a persistent vulnerability that is hard to eliminate. Enterprise security best practices, such as the NIST CSF³ or the Zero Trust model⁴, or even the recent

² DOGANA (GA No. 653618), www.dogana-project.eu

³ See Cybersecurity Framework | NIST, <https://www.nist.gov/cyberframework>

⁴ See Zero Trust Model - Modern Security Architecture | Microsoft Security, <https://www.microsoft.com/en-us/security/business/zero-trust>

EU NIS2 directive⁵, consider the human element. However, it can be necessary to communicate what the correct measurement of related risks is and where those risks lie. Since adopting a continuous security approach, risk must be understood and anticipated but cannot be eliminated. Cybersecurity best practices emphasise the importance of continuously estimating cyber risks, including those related to human behaviour. A modernised training process should align with these standards.

1.3 PA and human-related risk reduction.

PA originated as an analytical HR approach to managing people at work. It has been successfully used to enhance workforce processes and promote employee skills [17]. PA refers to the gathering and use of talent data to improve key talent and business outcomes (see Fig. 2). Data-driven insights for HR Teams, guide talent decisions, improve workforce processes, and enhance the overall employee experience. Recently, there has been a notable trend among companies to adopt PA more widely in areas such as recruitment and selection, performance management, and training and development [12] [13] [6].

Fig. 2. High-level concept of PA in cybersecurity.

From a general point of view, HR data analytics involves handling sensitive employee information. Managing and restricting access on a need-to-know basis is crucial for maintaining trust in HR analytics and processes. Privacy requirements are met by complying with regulations like GDPR and PDPA. Nonetheless, a recent study [14] underlined the so-called “dark side of PA”, which refers to the potential misuse or unethical application of PA in specific contexts. We recognise the importance of balancing ethical considerations and ATM's specific requirements while maximising the use of data for security purposes.

The first challenge was to integrate PA within the Training Process defined in Fig. 1, as shown in Fig. 3 transforming it into a risk-driven process.

⁵ Directive on measures for a high common level of cybersecurity across the Union, <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/nis2-directive>

Fig. 3. The role of PA within the Training Process and optimisation of the steps by risk_j.

1.4 From PA to Learning Analytics in Cybersecurity.

Learning Analytics (LA) represents an advanced subset of PA tailored explicitly for educational contexts. This field focuses on analysing learning data to profile trainees. It embodies a methodology for aggregating and deciphering the nuances of individual trainees' interactions within online learning environments [15].

The overarching objectives of learning analytics encompass the following: enhancing pedagogical strategies [13]; fostering active learner engagement [16]; identifying and supporting at-risk students [17]; investigating the determinants of course completion and overall student achievement [18].

LA is defined as the systematic process of measuring, collecting, analysing, and reporting data pertinent to learners and their environments. This process aims to facilitate a deeper understanding and enhancement of learning and its contexts [12]. LA refers to the analysis of learning data to profile students. It is a process of collecting and analysing the details of individual student interactions in online learning activities.

The primary objective of LA is to harness analytical methodologies to predict and identify students' specific learning needs, thereby enabling the formulation and refinement of educational strategies [12].

Fig. 4. Evolution of the People Analytics approach.

Various initiatives have been undertaken in existing literature to measure learning through digital data sets. However, integrating a comprehensive learning analytics framework into cybersecurity exercises remains notably absent [19] and it is the

evolution (see **Fig. 4**) that we pursue with this research. Our literature review did not find experiences demonstrating PA's efficacy in reducing human-related cyber risks using LA for cybersecurity [5].

2 Research Question.

Building on the basic concepts outlined in the Introduction, our research statement and questions can be summed up as follows.

Statement: ATMs, like other digitally enhanced businesses, are increasingly susceptible to cyber risks, especially those related to human factors. An effective training process can help mitigate these risks by focusing on high-risk individuals using clear prioritisation criteria. Nonetheless, the ongoing evolution of cybercrime indicates a need to transform the Training Process into one that is fully driven by cyber-risk considerations. A key performance indicator (KPI) for this process is ROTI, which comprehensively measures training costs related to the value of the trained personnel. The Kirkpatrick/Phillips model [20] [21] highlights that one significant cost arises from optimising class composition by identifying who needs to attend courses based on risk indicators.

Questions:

1. How can people's exposure to cyber risk be concretely and legally measured?
2. Can PA be an objective tool to optimise ROTI and reduce subjectivity in the training process?
3. How concretely does PA impact the overall training process?
4. Which Design assumptions must PA follow to be ethically and legally used in ATMs?

2.1 How to Measure Human-Related Cyber Risk.

The first research question is how people's exposure to cyber risk can be concretely and legally measured. This objective can be achieved by conducting individual risk assessments, which are calculated frequently enough using a continuous security approach. These assessments can be based on the results of phishing simulations, managed portfolio risk assessments, and preparedness, which can also be evaluated through questionnaires or by considering the specific position in the company. The results should then be used to tailor the best training programs - determining what to teach, to whom and how. This way, the risk results can be paired with training to mitigate human cyber risks [8].

The efficiency of Human Posture as a metric hinges on its comprehensive risk assessment, which integrates static and dynamic human-related factors. This evaluation consists of a multidimensional evaluation that encompasses different variables: general demographic or social aspects, personal attributes, contextual factors, educational background, simulated performance, and cyber incident history [22] [23].

The theoretical base of our human risk model was explored in the EU-funded project DOGANA [11] [22] and HERMENEUT [24]. In DOGANA, we explored the possibility of simulating phishing attacks and collecting personal, performance, and value metrics about individuals while ensuring compliance with ethical, privacy, and labour regulations. Human capital is typically classified as an intangible asset. However, people also have the potential to impact other intangible assets, such as brand and reputation. We have adopted cyber risk models for intangible assets developed in HERMENEUT.

The Human Risk Model (HRM) measures the human risk associated with each person or a set of people (clusters) within a business context. During the SEC-AIRSPACE project, we will develop an HRM model for ATMs to show that PA can facilitate risk management by mapping employees on Boston-Square maps.

The HRM consists of a human risk matrix that frames the risk related to each person based on two weighted measurements and the results of an asset management system already in use for cyber risk management systems (e.g. we used a prioritisation of assets using the well-known Crown Jewel Analysis methodology, mapping the handlers, i.e. the people who have access to them, including intangible assets):

HRM is a comprehensive system that considers various risk factors and is composed of three axis:

- Human Posture: This measure represents the risk factor associated with the person, considering their courses, phishing simulation results, etc.
- Organisational Impact: This measure represents the risk factor associated with the relationship between the company and the person (assets managed, roles, responsibilities, etc.).
- Cyber Attack Exposure: This measure takes a snapshot of a person's exposure based on the current context of cybercrime and cyber-attacks (e.g., increased attention to financial departments, secretaries, etc.).

The third element of this model, Cyber Attack Exposure, is calculated based on the frequency and severity of cyber-attacks in these domains using a Threat Intelligence service. It empirically measures a person's exposure and uses the CAPEC classification: Software, Hardware, Communication, Social Engineering, Physical Security, and Supply Chain.

As an initial seed for the calculation of the HRM, we used HAIS-Q, which literature reports as a valuable methodology for the pre-assessment of people's preparedness for Information Security [25] [26]. Moreover, we excluded from the model several parameters commonly used to measure susceptibility (e.g. gender, character traits such as empathy, etc.) because these data are subject to GDPR, and the literature does not agree on which parameters are relevant [27]. See **Table 1**.

The model is currently under development. However, given the difficulties in finding an analytical correlation among the different variables, we will use weighted Machine Learning to classify the HRM dataspace and extract the natural clusters of the single risk factors.

Table 1. Elements of the Human Risk Models adopted.

General Characteristics	This refers to general classification information about the person, e.g. gender, seniority, age, etc.
Personal Characteristics	This refers to subjective classification information, i.e., invariant elements related to the person, such as educational level or results of psychometric tests (e.g., HAIS-Q, R-HAIS-Q or Security Awareness Proficiency Assessment -SAPA- are all alternatives).
Situational Context	This is the work context in which the person operates, e.g., remote work vs. in-office work (e.g., for ATMs, there is an entirely different impact between blue collars and ATCOs).
Course History	This refers to the training courses attended in the past (or ongoing) by each person.
Individual Training Results	This refers to training performance, typically measured through Satisfaction Surveys, Pre-Assessments, and Post-Assessments (we used the Kirkpatrick/Phillip Model [7])
Simulation Results	This refers to the results of attack simulations (a.k.a CSX) that people have participated in (e.g., results of phishing campaigns and execution methods, results of other simulations like Table-Top Simulations, etc.)
Cyber Event History	This refers to anomalies from the SOC related to devices and equipment the person manages (e.g., smartphones, workstations, etc.).

All these elements are presented in the PA dashboard on a Boston Square map, see **Fig. 5**.

Fig. 5. Overview of the primary risk map used in the PA dashboard.

2.2 ROTI Optimisation and Reduction of Subjectivity in the Training Process.

In the ATM context, there is ample evidence that managers are concerned with the significance of improving productivity and performance due to the training programs [28]. Given a human-related cyber risk (e.g., the reduction of phishing susceptibility) and a desired percentage of reduction (e.g., above 50% or reduction), the HR department's **typical approach would usually involve the entire population** with training or some other subjective criteria [7] [29]. This leads to a flat or non-optimal approach that can statistically cover the risky part of the population (e.g., trawl fishing) because the risky individuals cannot be identified in advance.

Isolating risky groups allows, instead, to focus the training campaigns (i.e., involving fewer people) and reduce costs while maintaining the same risk reduction [26]. To this aim, it is useful to report the conclusions of a recent paper [30], which gives an insight into the role of PA in the project to focus on educational needs and appropriate goal setting:

*“It should be noted that the holding of these training programs was not predetermined with a specific strategy and program and was voluntary and spontaneous and based on the attractions created during the series of training programs. Therefore, **in the future, it is necessary to focus on educational needs assessment and appropriate goal setting.** In addition, the goals should be pursued step by step with continuous monitoring and evaluation, and shortcomings and improvements should be addressed during implementation”.*

Addressing the complexity inherent in defining key performance indicators (KPIs) to evaluate the tangible benefits of adopting PA within organisations is the challenge we propose to solve through ROTI Calculation. A robust and comprehensive definition of these KPIs is critical for assessing the advantages organisations garner through PA. As delineated in a recent study [30], the utility of high prediction accuracy is emphasised, enabling managers to engage in informed, forward-looking decision-making. we aim to calculate the ROTI level in the Kirkpatrick Model by comparing the class's proportions with and without PA. The value should be the ratio between the class using classic HR criteria and the class using PA criteria, multiplied by the percentage. As for costs, we will consider the paper model [30].

The resulting Learning Analytics pyramid is reported in **Fig. 6**.

Fig. 6. Learning Analytics Pyramid.

Furthermore, it's worth noting that using PA allows us to accurately measure the impact of specific training programs. This is done by conducting a counterfactual analysis to show the potential effects of these training interventions. To do this, we need a large enough sample size to compare groups of employees with similar socio-cultural characteristics, some who participated in specific training courses and some who did not, and assess the differences in their performance over time.

Our experiment will measure Kirkpatrick's levels 1, 2, 3, and 5. Levels 1 and 2 are the norm in most learning and training design processes, while level 3 is less common. Level 5 approximates the ROI for the specific project's context. Level 3 verification is done via a CSX exercise (e.g., attack simulator or HAIS-Q Questionnaires or Table-Top simulations [4]). Level 4 will not be measured because it is usually meant to measure the impact of training on business and, therefore, the training KPIs at this level. The measurement is performed with interviews after several months.

Given a defined risk reduction, the organisation's global ROTI is the multiplication of individual ROTI and the probability of the individual being a risky subject.

$$ROTI_{organisation}(risk) = \sum_{\forall person} (ROTI_K(person) \cdot P(person|risk)) \quad (1)$$

Where:

$ROTI_K(person)$ is Kirkpatrick's definition of ROTI for a given person.

$P(person|risk)$ is the conditional probability that a given person will attend a training track, given that he is exposed to a specific risk. This value is calculated using HRM.

$ROTI_{organisation}(risk)$ is the sum of individual $ROTI_K$.

Given a specific risk, PA maximises P and then the ROTI (i.e., training effectiveness) by selecting only people exposed to specific cyber risks. This way, ROTI becomes an organisation's "Key Performance Indicator".

PA will collect individual $ROTI_K(person)$ on all the attendants (i.e., Kirkpatrick's levels 1, 2 and 3) and, after checking who would have been selected by PA, compare

the different costs while keeping the same cyber risk reduction. The current methodology relies on the observation that HR departments typically mandate training for the entire workforce **without employing more precise or objective criteria** [7] [29].

2.3 Design criteria of PA in the ATM context.

The PA solution requires integrating various data sources. It is important to link HR data with data about the skills necessary for specific roles, data related to ownership or connection to assets with a cyber risk index, data concerning performance against cyber risk, and data about attendance at specific training or educational events. Performance data should be evaluated both before and after training.

The assumption is that current and future behaviour can be explained and predicted from the analysis of past actions and their consequences [31]. Our approach to PA does not involve predicting behaviour from past data like normally happens in People Analytics but is used only to spot problematic patterns to support the decision of HR or CISO.

Problems with PA analytics.

Literature reports [14] different possible abuses of PA and LA. The so-called “dark side of PA” refers to the potential misuse or unethical application of PA in specific contexts. We limited the PA using the categories described in [14], as follows.

- Descriptive analytics – examine what occurred in the past and how this influences the present by answering the question “What happened?” – we present elaborated data visualisation dashboards about the present status of data, with eventually limited statistical analysis (i.e., regression, weighted average, deviations, etc)
- Predictive analytics – identifying explanatory patterns (such as trends, relationships, preferences, clusters) from past or present events to forecast future business developments – we based this service on explainable ML clustering algorithms. Based on the integration with solution-oriented simulation and scenario calculations.
- Prescriptive analytics –forecasts future development and recommends decisions and courses of action based on analysing past data and alternative future scenarios – we are not using AI to forecast future behaviour; we just present the data to the operator (HR) to augment and de-bias its analytical process. The aim is to raise the efficiency of core human resources functions such as workforce planning, recruiting, development and training, as well as to optimise employees’ and the organisations’ performance [32]. The problem of algorithms biases is quite challenging at the present state of maturation.
- Autonomous analytics – autonomous learning algorithms, primarily based on artificial neural networks to process structured, unstructured, and self-updating data from various sources – we make no usage of complex predictive AI models to avoid unfairness, misuse and ethical implications in general. The issue is quite problematic and needs additional research. However, the cyber risk reduction scenario avoids common ethical pitfalls such as interfering with career progression. Nonetheless, we

are aware that Human Resource Analytics is foreseen to transform the People Analytics sector [4]. PA can create an illusion of control and reductionism: PA builds on the belief that digital data can accurately represent reality and objectively quantify workforces.

Selected design patterns.

From the data flow availability point of view, the main challenge in this project is assessing the availability of such data and the possibility of analysing it while ensuring privacy protection. The goal is to monitor whether providing certain groups with training can enhance business performance and reduce risks.

To establish a strong and scientifically sound approach to cyber risk management, it is crucial to integrate PA with existing methodologies in the field, such as SecRAM or ATT&CK. This process should acknowledge that assets encompass any valuable entities that require protection, including human assets, highlighting the importance of addressing human-related vulnerabilities and errors [1].

It is also essential that PA is designed to seamlessly weave human-centric cyber risk management elements with the broader spectrum of cyber risk management strategies already in place. This integration enhances ATM's security posture and ensures a more resilient infrastructure against cyber threats.

Central to this effort is the system's prioritisation of explainability and accountability. Accountability is important, as it requires individuals to clearly state and justify their actions, motivations, and the reasoning behind their decisions. When it comes to incorporating autonomous analytics in people management, there is a potential risk for organisations to avoid accountability. To address this, the machine learning models used by PA must be transparent. Avoiding opaque, autonomous analytics helps maintain accountability and promotes a culture of clear, justifiable decision-making. Usage of PA has some perils, as underlined in a recent paper [14]. Below is a summary of our design criteria.

- Reduce the ethical and legal implications.
 - Applying People Analytics to human-related cyber risk mitigation has fewer ethical and legal implications than other cases (e.g., evaluating possible career advancement).
- Reduce the impact of false positives (persons wrongly considered at risk).
 - In our case, the mitigation action highlighted by the PA does not lead to problems if administered, even in excess, to false positives (a little extra training doesn't hurt anyone).
 - Even in the case of model inaccuracies (false negatives), the consequence is NOT to administer mitigation. However, it must be considered that shortcomings are inherent in the very nature of the case, as with any cybersecurity and risk estimation solution.
- Reduce the marginalisation of human sense-making, reasoning, and rationalising.
 - The increasing transfer of traditional management tasks to people analytics systems can marginalise decision-makers' mental representations, sense-making and rationality. For this reason, the automation level is reduced, and we

introduced the term “Augmented HR”, which represents the logical concept of HR using the PA service. This is extremely important to keep human decision-makers in the loop.

- Compensate inefficient HR decision-making
 - Help managers make more effective HR decisions to complement their competencies and promote rationality in managerial decision-making and human sense-making.
 - Avoid reducing too much the relevance and need for genuine human decision-making competencies, not creating an automatic tool
- Unfairness of training and lock-in effect
 - Based on PA predictions, an ATM might allocate training resources only to the employees they perceive at risk, which will result in selected employees receiving additional training, while others receive no training. Such actions will produce exactly the predicted results: employees who receive training will outperform those who do not receive training. However, the difference between the two groups of employees can mistakenly be interpreted as an indicator of the validity of people analytics, while the performance improvement might be due to the additional training and not related to people analytics’ predictive power.
 - When utilising predictions derived from PA, there is a risk that an ATM organisation might disproportionately allocate training resources. This allocation is often biased towards employees perceived as being at risk, leading to a scenario where a select group receives additional training while others are neglected. This selective allocation inadvertently confirms the initial predictions, as employees who have received additional training tend to outperform their untrained counterparts. This observable performance disparity might be erroneously cited as evidence supporting the accuracy of PA predictions. It is essential to recognise that such improvements in performance are primarily attributed to the extra training rather than the predictive accuracy of PA.
 - The ML model must be explainable, and GUI supports understanding the rationale of the proposed actions and underline the disparities in training efforts.
- Link with existing cyber risk methodologies (e.g., SecRAM or ATT&CK)
 - Humans are assets; an asset is something valuable that needs protection, and a vulnerability is an asset’s error and weakness.
 - PA should integrate human-related cyber risk management loops with existing cyber risk management methodologies.
- Maintain Explainability and Accountability
 - Accountability refers to the expectation that a person can be called on to justify his or her intentions, motives and rationalities. By allocating decision-making authority to autonomous people analytics, organisations could be tempted to avoid accountability
 - ML model must not be opaque, and PA will not perform autonomous analytics
- Maintain Privacy and its perception
 - Data must be fully anonymized, and our practices comply with GDPR regulations. However, even when analyses are fully legal from a privacy standpoint, HR managers should consider whether employees might view these

practices as violations of their privacy and unethical, which could lead to demotivation. In fact, many researchers [33] have shown that automated access to employees' personal information for performance management can decrease their motivation levels, ultimately undermining the objectives of people analytics.

- Link Cybersecurity exercises (CSX) with Learning Analytics
 - CSX are a learning or training event in which individuals or teams implement, manage and defend/attack a network of computers at a tactical or strategic level. CSX always leaves an extensive digital footprint on the learning process [4].
 - We will use a CSX Learning Analytics Reference Model [4].

2.4 Experimentation setup and use cases.

Fig. 7 represents a simplified use case for an ATM that uses HAIS-Q as an employee risk assessment tool. This is the situation described in the paper [26]. **Fig. 8** reports a use case where a person is sent to a classroom because of his/her poor performance in each simulation scenario associated with the risk. This type of training and classroom composition is suboptimal because it is driven by evidence and HR perceptions. In these figures, $risk_j$ is any human-related risk defined by SecRAM taxonomy, T_j is the corresponding most appropriate Training (e.g. phishing risk and anti-phishing training). CSX is any type of cybersecurity exercise considered appropriate by the teacher for T_j and $risk_j$.

Fig. 7. Simplified use-case for an ATM that uses HAIS-Q as an employee risk assessment tool

Fig. 8. A simplified use case of an employee sent to attend a classroom because of his/her poor performance in each simulation scenario associated with a risk.

Fig. 9. Simplified use-case where the PA collects data for each person in the organisation, either history and less variant personal traits (e.g., role, cost of training, inherent cyber risk exposure).

Fig. 9 reports a use case where the PA collects data for each person in the organisation, either history or variant personal traits (e.g., role, cost of training, inherent cyber risk exposure). The PA suggests to HR who needs to attend training T_j before others, and the classroom proposed by the PA is sent to attend. After this phase, the teacher/trainer

will assign a CSX scenario corresponding to the T_j . The PA evaluates the trainee's performance to update the estimated risk exposure.

2.5 Machine Learning Approach.

Machine Learning offers significant advantages and opportunities in class composition, as it allows us to extract patterns, suggest HRM outlines, and induce employee partitions without previous knowledge, possibly in an unsupervised way. Furthermore, a subsequent supervised phase can be developed to test the identified patterns and class compositions against the actual post-course evaluations. Indeed, the approach we propose is twofold:

- At first, an **unsupervised learning phase** is developed: different clustering techniques (mainly considering partitioning and hierarchical methods) are tested on these data to find the most suitable one. This evaluation is performed, on the one hand, through statistical tests (e.g., Kruskal-Wallis and Mann-Whitney) and metrics comparison (e.g., Silhouette measure and within-cluster variability) and, on the other hand, taking into account human evaluation and practical suitability (i.e., if different partitions are mathematically sound, the number of clusters can be determined by also considering what solution would be more useful and easy to implement in the scenario).
- Then, a **supervised phase** for post-course evaluation is proposed: first, after the employees are (or are not) involved in the training, some statistical and qualitative considerations are drawn about the intersections between clustering-induced partitioning and HR selection (and their related post-course evaluation results). Furthermore, a supervised-ML-based validation is performed by leveraging the sample of trained employees to develop a model able to predict training outcomes based on pre-course information and then applying it to the (even not trained) employees in different clusters to see the forecasted results.

Of course, the ML approach must be aligned with the design criteria reported in Section 2.3, considering in particular the need for accountability, explainability, and fairness.

3 Early Results.

In this section, we report the early findings of PA's overall impact on the Training Process within the ATM context. The SEC-AIRSPACE project will continue and enter the experimentation phase in 2025. The Evaluation Research Plan has been defined and accepted by the funding body (SESAR JU).

3.1 Experimental assumption.

The role of PA is potentially more complex than merely reducing the number of individuals to be trained. PA should aim to identify an optimal cluster of individuals to

undergo risk-specific training to minimise the overall risk. The effectiveness of the Training Process, which PA is part of, results from several concurrent factors that reduce ROTI. We will do some working hypotheses on the training data and the provider to isolate PA's net effect.

- HR operates at its best; its decisions are made by leveraging its knowledge and comprehension of the overall training process' risks, costs, and consequences. The creation of training classes (i.e., the user segmentation) follows subjective or non-analytic criteria [6] [7].
- The training process is roughly composed of some phases: user segmentation, class composition, selection from a training catalogue of the best-matched course and Training Provider, pre-assessment, training attendance and post-assessment.

When attending a training session, each individual incurs different costs and has varied impacts on the organisation. We typically assume an average value for all employees. Still, it's essential to recognise that these differences could also be considered part of the individual cyber risks when estimating the Impact variable for a person.

3.2 Results.

We experimented with an ATM provider and contacted them through the SEC-AIRSPACE partners' community (not disclosed). The ATM employs approx. 300 people and regularly delivers cybersecurity classes, directly organised by HR. We conducted the experiment using a dual-track approach. Collaborating with the EU project CYRUS, we offered free training for all at-risk individuals, with no extra costs aside from course attendance. Simultaneously, we started data collection and analysis using the PA software. We evaluated all employees using our model, administering HAIS-Q and collecting additional data (see Section 2.1). **Fig. 10** shows the initial HAIS-Q results, categorising employees into management (48 people, e.g. admin, director, head of *), operational (275 people, AFIS, ATCO AFIS/CNS, APRON Manager, ATC supervisor, technicians), and training (56 people, e.g., roles of head of ATC simulators, pseudopilot, student ACTO)⁶. The reliability analysis of collected HAIS-Q, used Cronbach's alpha and composite reliability scores [34] [35]: all the alpha and composite reliability scores were above .70 [36] [37] and then considered reliable. The HAIS-Q investigation highlighted both strengths and weaknesses in their average preparation.

All employees were mapped using a Boston Square map, comparing HR selections with PA suggestions. **Fig. 11** shows two risk maps, each bullet representing a person: on the left, the individuals selected by HR, evaluated with HRM; on the right, all employees, with a highlight indicating the riskiest ones. **Fig. 11** indicates that HR's criteria were suboptimal, as the selected individuals spanned the risk map, with some in the yellow (low-risk) area. PA suggests forming a more focused group of truly at-risk trainees with little overlap.

⁶ We collected data also about one support employee: the cleaner.

Fig. 10. HAIS-Q Segmentation by Role Cluster before the training.

Fig. 11. Comparison of risk maps for HR-selected employees for training versus all employees. The left shows HR-selected, the right shows everyone, and the green rectangle highlights those PA evaluates more at-risk.

The second validation step was executed with the people selected by the HR performing a post-training HRM evaluation, using data from a second round of HAIS-Q and Kirkpatrick’s Level 1 questionnaires. In the left half of **Fig. 12**, the blue line represents pre-training scores, and the orange line represents post-training HRM for each trainee. The graph shows heterogeneous improvements. **Fig. 12** right side displays the difference between the pre and post HRM for each trainee. This second graph better shows the training impact, values above zero mean decreasing HRM because of training. This visualization also help to spot the trainees for which the session was not beneficial.

Fig. 12. Graph of pre- and post-training evaluation of HRM for each trainee selected by HR (without the support of PA).

4 Further discussions.

A review of prior literature highlights the nature of training efforts comprised of “one-size-fits-all” and “cookie-cutter” education programs that are compliance-based do not produce long-term results [38]. Utilising PA for strategically implementing training initiatives is an effective mitigation tool in enhancing organisational cybersecurity posture. By employing data-driven strategies, organisations can precisely identify the employee segments most in need of training, thereby ensuring that these interventions achieve maximum impact regarding cybersecurity improvements. This targeted approach elevates the organisation's overall security resilience and optimises resource allocation by minimising the associated costs, engagement challenges, and participation efforts required. According to a recent study [8], tailored training programs based on advanced analytics can significantly improve learning outcomes and behavioural change in corporate settings, which is critical for effective cybersecurity measures. Literature reports the cost-benefit advantages of applying PA to training, highlighting its role in sharpening an organisation's competitive edge through enhanced security measures [16]. By adopting a nuanced, analytics-driven approach to employee training, organisations can fortify their cybersecurity defences while ensuring efficient use of their resources. The term "PA" refers not to technology but rather to a modern, quantitative, evidence-based, and data-driven approach to managing the workforce [17].

HRM would help analyse and predict people's reliability and behaviour in the workplace, but it is not fully automated personal data processing. HRM indeed works with machine learning technology. However, the decisions impacting on the employees, such as suggesting a new course or training, would still be in the hands of other people, such as the Human Resources department. Therefore, HRM would not fall under Article 22 GDPR, according to which “*The data subject shall have the right not to be subject to a decision based solely on automated processing, including profiling, which produces legal effects concerning him or her or similarly significantly affects him or her.*” As described in this paper, People Analytics would instead be classified as semi-automated data processing.

Furthermore, People Analytics would not be considered a form of Artificial Intelligence as defined by the AI Act under Article 3 (1). Namely, an ‘AI system’ is defined as “*a machine-based system that is designed to operate with varying levels of autonomy and that may exhibit adaptiveness after deployment, and that, for explicit or implicit objectives, infers, from the input it receives, how to generate outputs such as predictions, content, recommendations, or decisions that can influence physical or virtual environments.*” If a level of autonomy is detected in the HRM, the essential element of adaptiveness after deployment is currently missing. The assessment would have to be repeated wherever the tool had to be changed and deployed differently, showing adaptiveness. In that case, particular caution would have to be dedicated to the norm forbidding social scoring, resulting in detrimental or unfavourable treatment under Article 5 (1) (c).

Acknowledgements. This project has received funding from the SESAR Joint Undertaking under the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreements no 101114635.

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